

Preparation of some 3-Chloro-substituted-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones

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Although 2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones with different substituents at 3- and 5-positions of the ring have been prepared earlier, yet no synthesis of piperidin-4-ones with halo substitution in any one of these positions is reported so far. We report in this communication the preparation of some 3-chloro-substituted-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones (1–6). The chloropiperidinones were prepared following the available methods¹, i.e. by the condensation of acetone (chloroacetone in the present case) with aromatic aldehydes and ammonia.

This method of synthesis stands as the direct route for obtaining 3-chloropiperidin-4-ones. In the alternative method, chlorination of the corresponding piperidin-4-ones leads to *N*-chloropiperidinones². The reactions, viz. *N*-methylation using methyl iodide and dry acetone in the presence of potassium carbonate and elimination using triethylamine and acetic acid, have been carried out on 1 and the products 7 and 8 respectively were obtained. The formation of 8 is the result of the β -elimination of HCl from 1³. The most probable structure is 8a in which there is conjugation among carbonyl group, double bond and aromatic chromophore, and the other isomer 8b if at all formed will be formed in small amount only.

Assignment of structures to all the compounds was made on the basis of IR, ¹H nmr, ¹³C nmr and mass spectral data.

Experimental

The compounds were routinely checked for their purity by tlc on silica gel G. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra on a Varian XL-300 spectrometer (at the University of Missouri, U.S.A.) and mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH 7 spectrometer at 70 eV. Melting points are uncorrected.

3-Chloro-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones (1–6). Typical procedure: A mixture of chloroacetone (5.0 g, 0.05 mol), benzaldehyde (10.6 g, 0.1 mol) and anhydrous ammonium acetate (3.85 g, 0.05 mol) in ethanol (95%, 5 ml) was heated on a water-bath with constant shaking until the contents became

- 1 ; Ar = Ph
- 2 ; Ar = *o*-CH₃OC₆H₄
- 3 ; Ar = *p*-CH₃OC₆H₄
- 4 ; Ar = *o*-ClC₆H₄
- 5 ; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄
- 6 ; Ar = *p*-MeC₆H₄

pale orange. It was then cooled and treated with ether. The solid formed was filtered off. To the clear filtrate concentrated HCl (2.5 ml) was added to get the hydrochloride of piperidone. The hydrochloride was washed with ethanol-ether (1:5) mixture. The free base was obtained by treating a suspension of the hydrochloride in acetone with aqueous ammonia, followed by dilution with water. It was recrystallised from ethanol, (1; 35%), m.p. 107–08°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 725 (CO) and 740 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 2.98 (2H, d, C-CH₂), 2.15 (1H, s, NH), 3.30 (1H, m, ArCH-CH₂), 3.60 (1H, d, Ar-CH-C(Cl)-), 4.80 (1H, d, -CH(Cl)-CO-) and 7.30–7.48 (10H, m, ArH); ^{13}C nmr δ 199.0 (C-4), 141.5, 139.7 and 128–126 (phenyl carbons), 68.89 (C-2), 68.39 (C-6), 66.83 (C-3) and 50.66 ppm (C-5); m/z 28 (M^+), 287 ($M^+ + 2$) and 250 ($M^+ - \text{Cl}$); 3-chloro-2,6-bis(o-methoxyphenyl)piperidin-4-one (2; 32%), m.p. 130–32°; ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) δ 2.91–2.93 (2H, d, -C-CH₂-), 3.3 (1H, hump, NH), 3.86–3.89 (6H, 2s, OCH₃), 4.3–4.4 (2H, 2d, 2 × Ar-CH), 4.97–5.0 (1H, d, -CH(Cl)-CO-) and 6.8–7.4 (8H, m, ArH); ^{13}C nmr δ 200.3 (C-4), 157.2, 156.6, 129–127, 120, 111 and 110 (Ph-C), 66.8 (C-2), 65.0 (C-6), 57.1 (C-3), 49.2 (C-5) and 55.4–55.2 ppm (O-CH₃); 3-chloro-2,6-bis(p-methoxyphenyl)piperidin-4-one (3; 34%), m.p. 119–120°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 720 (CO) and 740 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 1.92 (1H, s, NH), 2.45–2.52 (2H, d, ArCHCH₂CO), 3.56 (6H, s, -OCH₃), 3.5–3.7 (1H, d, ArCH-C(Cl)-), 3.80–3.88 (1H, d, ArCHCH₂) 4.25–4.35 (1H, d, CH(Cl)-C=O) and 6.75–7.2 (8H, m, ArH); 3-chloro-2,6-bis(o-chlorophenyl)piperidin-4-one (4; 32%), m.p. 135°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 295 (NH), 1 710 (CO) and 745 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); 3-chloro-2,6-bis(p-chlorophenyl)piperidin-4-one (5; 38%), m.p. 171–172°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 310 (NH), 1 710 (CO) and 745 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 2.00 (1H, s, NH), 2.65–2.70 (1H, d, ArCHCH₂CO), 3.80–3.90 (1H, d, Ar-CH-C(Cl)-), 4.00–4.10 (1H, dd, ArCH-CH₂CO), 4.38–4.48 (1H, d, CH(Cl)-CO) and 7.30–7.40 (8H, m, ArH); 3-chloro-2,6-bis(p-methylphenyl)piperidin-4-one (5; 38%), m.p. 132–33°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 295 (NH), 1 715 (CO) and 750 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 1.8–1.9 (1H, hump, NH), 2.40–2.46 (2H, d, ArCHCH₂CO), 3.54–3.64 (1H, d, Ar-CH-C(Cl)-), 3.7–3.8 (1H, dd, ArCHCH₂), 4.18–4.28 (1H, d, -CH(Cl)-CO) and 6.8–7.22 (8H, m, ArH).

N-Methyl-3-chloro-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (7):
To a mixture of 1 (400 mg, 0.0014 mol) and

dry acetone (8 ml) was added anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.6 g, 0.01 mol) and the contents were refluxed on a water-bath. Four portions of methyl iodide (0.4 g, 0.002 mol) in dry acetone (0.4 ml) were added to the reaction mixture in 2 h durations and the refluxing was continued for another 4 h. The mixture was then filtered and the acetone solution was evaporated. The product was crystallised from ethanol, (380 mg, 90%), m.p. 135–37°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 735 (CO), 1 235 (N-CH₃) and 740 cm^{-1} (C-Cl), absence of sharp band at 300 cm^{-1} showed the absence of NH stretching which appeared in compound 1; ^1H nmr δ 1.79 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 2.75–2.80 (1H, dd, CH₂CO), 2.91–3.0 (1H, dd, CH₂CO), 3.40–3.44 (2H, d, Ar-CH-C(Cl)-), 3.50–3.54 (1H, dd, ArCHCH₂), 4.71–4.74 (1H, d, -CH(Cl)-CO-) and 7.31–7.46 (10H, m, ArH); ^{13}C nmr δ 198.22 (C-4), 142.1, 140.2, 128.9–126.9 (Ph-C), 69.7 (C-2), 68.1 (C-6), 49.7 (C-5) and 41.1 ppm (N-CH₃); m/z 299 (M^+), 301 ($M^+ + 2$ peak with 33% intensity).

2,5-Diphenyl-5,6-dihydro-3H-pyridin-4-one (8):
A mixture of compound 1 (100 mg, 0.4 mmol), glacial acetic acid (200 mg, 3 mmol) and triethylamine (44 mg, 0.4 mmol) taken in DMSO (3 ml) solvent was refluxed for 2 h in a water-bath. It was then cooled, water (10 ml) added and a few drops of ammonia. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (51%), m.p. 118–19°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 75 (CO), 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N), absence of a band at 3 300 cm^{-1} showed the absence of NH stretching which appeared in compound 1; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 2.27–2.34 (1H, d, Ar-C-CH₂CO), 2.78–2.79 (1H, d, Ar-C-CH₂CO), 3.24–3.25 (1H, d, Ar-C-CH₂CO) 4.64–4.67 (1H, d, Ar-CCH₂CO) and 7.23–7.39 (10H, m, ArH); m/z 249 (M^+).

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